

PARENTAL KNOWLEDGE, AWARENESS, AND PREVENTIVE PRACTICES REGARDING BETA THALASSEMIA: A STUDY FROM PESHAWAR, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the knowledge and awareness of parents of Beta thalassemia children about thalassemia disease in Peshawar, registered with Fatimid Foundation, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Methodology: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Fatimid Foundation, Peshawar. Using a non-probability convenience sampling technique, 274 parents of children with thalassemia were enrolled. Data was collected through a pre-designed questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 22. Statistical tests, including the Chi-square test, were applied to assess associations between demographic variables and knowledge levels.

Results: Among 274 participants, 55.47% were male and 44.53% female. Age distribution showed 9.85% (20-25 years), 31.02% (25-30 years), 28.83% (30-35 years), and 30.29% (40 years or above). The majority demonstrated good knowledge: 70.44% knew thalassemia is genetic, 76.3% understood proper treatment enables normal life, and 76.64% recognized blood transfusion as treatment. However, knowledge gaps existed 49.27% incorrectly believed surgery can treat thalassemia, 41.24% were unaware that complications arise from iron overload, and 34.67% lacked understanding of thalassemia minor. Regarding prevention, 57.66% recognized consanguineous marriage risks, 68.98% understood inheritance patterns, and only 37.2% had undergone premarital testing. Chi-square analysis revealed a significant association between premarital testing and knowledge levels ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: While parents of thalassemic children demonstrate reasonable awareness, significant knowledge gaps exist regarding disease complications, inheritance patterns, and preventive measures. The findings emphasize the urgent need for government-led awareness campaigns, premarital screening programs, and public education to reduce thalassemia prevalence in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Thalassemia is a group of autosomal recessive genetic disorders characterized by reduced or absent synthesis of globin chains; it can either involve α or β globin synthesis, leading to ineffective erythropoiesis resulting in premature destruction of red blood cells with varying degrees of anemia from an asymptomatic mild form to severe life-threatening conditions requiring lifelong medical management [1]. Beta-thalassemia results from mutations in the β -globin genes situated on chromosome 11 and manifests three clinical forms depending on genotype and modifier mutations that are classified as thalassemia major (the most severe form, which presents in infancy with hemolytic anemia and hepatosplenomegaly), intermedia (moderate severity), and minor (the asymptomatic carrier state) [2].

Thalassemia has a high global burden, with around 60,000 affected newborns every year and an estimated 3% of the world population carrying beta-thalassemia genes. The disease is most prevalent in regions such as the Mediterranean, Southeast Asia, Central Asia, the Indian subcontinent, and the Middle East. In Pakistan, approximately 9 million beta-thalassemia carriers account for 5-8% of the population; this results in about 5,000 births of new cases requiring transfusion-dependent thalassemia treatment annually and an estimated total of 100,000 existing cases, equating to about 5% of all thalassemia patients worldwide [3]. Clinical manifestations include severe anemia, growth retardation, delayed puberty, bone deformities, hepatosplenomegaly, jaundice, iron overload from repeated transfusions, and complications affecting the heart, liver, and endocrine systems. In thalassemia major, iron overload is the joint outcome of multiple blood transfusions and inappropriately increased iron absorption associated with ineffective erythropoiesis, leading to oxidative stress, damaging mitochondria, lysosomes, lipid membranes, proteins, and DNA [4].

Diagnosis is based on hemoglobin electrophoresis showing increased HbF and HbA2 fractions with decreased HbA, radiological findings supported

by abdominal ultrasonography that reveal splenomegaly and cholelithiasis [2]. Management consists of regular blood transfusions to maintain adequate hemoglobin levels, iron chelation therapy for preventing complications from iron overload, and in selected cases, splenectomy or bone marrow transplantation, which is the only curative option [1]. Prevention strategies involving public education on carrier screening, genetic counseling, and premarital testing have been very effective in reducing the birth of thalassemia major babies in countries where it has high prevalence [5]. Consanguineous marriage is the major reason leading to a high incidence of disease in Pakistan; hereditary diseases are largely linked to familial marriages, particularly cousins marrying cousins [6].

Pakistan is still facing challenges in thalassemia control due to limited public awareness, high rates of consanguineous marriages, inadequate screening programs, and insufficient health infrastructure despite available interventions. Recent studies in Malakand Division revealed that only 66% of respondents had knowledge about thalassemia, and 63% reported intermarriages in their families [7]. The rationale for this study is to assess knowledge and awareness levels among parents of affected children; such a population would be both caregivers managing the disease daily, as well as potential educators within their communities. Previous studies conducted in Pakistan were limited by small sample sizes or general population studies rather than affected families [8]. This study will evaluate the knowledge and awareness of parents of beta thalassemia children registered with Fatimid Foundation, Peshawar, to identify gaps in understanding that can be used to design targeted interventions for disease prevention and control within the region.

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Fatimid Foundation, Hayatabad, Peshawar, targeting parents of thalassemia-affected children registered with the foundation who belonged to Peshawar. Using the Raosoft

online sample size calculator, a sample of 274 participants was calculated from the total registered population of 1,200 thalassemia children, and participants were selected through a non-probability convenience sampling technique based on the inclusion criteria of parents with registered beta thalassemia children, while excluding parents of children with other types of thalassemia or those not registered with the foundation. Ethical approval was obtained from the School of Health Science, Peshawar Research Institutional Review Board, with Letter of Authorization (Ethical no.920) from Fatimid Foundation, and verbal informed consent was secured from all participants [9]. Data collection employed a pre-designed questionnaire translated into Urdu and local languages, covering demographic information, knowledge domains about thalassemia, including genetic basis, treatment options, complications, prevention strategies, and awareness of inheritance patterns and premarital screening, with all questions being

closed-ended. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 22, employing descriptive statistics to calculate frequencies and percentages for all variables, while Chi-square tests were applied to determine associations between demographic characteristics (age, gender, premarital testing status) and knowledge levels, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics

A total of 274 parents of thalassemic children participated in the study. The demographic distribution revealed male predominance with 152 (55.47%) males and 122 (44.53%) females. Age distribution showed that 27 participants (9.85%) were aged 20-25 years, 85 (31.02%) were 25-30 years, 79 (28.83%) were 30-35 years, and 83 (30.29%) were 40 years or above. Regarding premarital testing practices, only 102 participants (37.2%) had undergone thalassemia testing before marriage, while 172 (62.8%) had not.

Knowledge and Awareness Levels

Table 1: Knowledge Regarding Basic Disease Characteristics

Knowledge Question	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Correct Response
Is thalassemia a genetic disease?	193 (70.44)	81 (29.56)	70.44%
Have you ever heard of thalassemia?	252 (92.0)	22 (8.0)	92.0%
Can blood test identify thalassemia?	216 (78.8)	58 (21.2)	78.8%
Which is the most common thalassemia?	134 (48.9)	140 (51.1)	48.9%

Most participants demonstrated good foundational knowledge, with 70.44% correctly identifying thalassemia as a genetic disorder and

92% having heard about the disease. However, only 48.9% correctly identified beta-thalassemia as the most common type.

Table 2: Knowledge Regarding Treatment and Management

Treatment Knowledge	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Correct Response
Individuals with thalassemia can live a normal life with proper treatment	209 (76.3)	65 (23.7)	76.3%
Can a patient survive if thalassemia is untreated?	49 (17.9)	225 (82.1)	82.1%
Thalassemia can be treated with blood transfusions	210 (76.64)	64 (23.36)	76.64%
Thalassemia can be treated with surgery	139 (50.73)	135 (49.27)	49.27%
Treatment available that can cure thalassemia	200 (73.0)	74 (27.0)	27.0%
Problems in thalassemia major due to iron overload and multiple transfusions	162 (59.12)	112 (40.88)	59.12%

Regarding treatment knowledge, 76.3% understood that proper treatment enables normal life, and 82.1% correctly recognized that untreated thalassemia is fatal. While 76.64% knew about blood transfusion therapy, only

49.27% correctly understood that surgery is not a treatment option. Notably, only 27% correctly recognized that no cure currently exists for thalassemia, and just 59.12% understood the role of iron overload in disease complications.

Table 3: Knowledge Regarding Complications

Complication Knowledge	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Correct Response
Does thalassemia lead to other diseases (heart, liver, bones, spleen, lungs)?	192 (70.07)	82 (29.93)	70.07%

More than two-thirds (70.07%) of participants were aware that thalassemia can lead to complications affecting multiple organ systems,

including the heart, liver, bones, spleen, and lungs.

Table 4: Awareness Regarding Genetic Inheritance and Prevention

Inheritance and Prevention Awareness	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Correct Response
Inter-family marriages may lead to thalassemia	158 (57.66)	116 (42.34)	57.66%
Do both parents need to have thalassemia minor for the baby to have thalassemia major?	189 (68.98)	85 (31.02)	68.98%
If one parent has thalassemia minor, chance of having a child with the disease?	137 (50.0)	137 (50.0)	50.0%
Does person with thalassemia minor lead a healthy life?	179 (65.33)	95 (34.67)	65.33%
Do you think thalassemia is preventable?	171 (62.41)	103 (37.59)	62.41%
Have you or anyone you know had premarital testing?	102 (37.23)	172 (62.77)	37.23%
Have you or anyone you know from a cousin's marriage had a child with thalassemia?	156 (56.93)	118 (43.07)	56.93%
Do you think premarital testing should be mandatory?	159 (58.03)	115 (41.97)	58.03%

Genetic inheritance awareness showed that 68.98% understood the autosomal recessive pattern requiring both parents to be carriers for an affected child, while 57.66% recognized consanguineous marriage as a risk factor. However, only 50% correctly understood carrier risk when one parent has thalassemia minor, and

34.67% were unaware that thalassemia minor individuals lead healthy lives. Regarding prevention, 62.41% believed thalassemia is preventable, yet only 37.23% had undergone premarital testing, although 58.03% supported making premarital testing mandatory.

Association Between Demographic Factors and Knowledge Levels

Table 5: Association Between Gender and Knowledge Levels (Chi-square Analysis)

Knowledge Indicator	Male (n=152) n (%)	Female (n=122) n (%)	p-value
Knowledge that thalassemia is genetic	112 (73.7)	81 (66.4)	0.189
Knowledge of the inheritance pattern	108 (71.1)	81 (66.4)	0.407
Awareness of consanguineous marriage risk	91 (59.9)	67 (54.9)	0.408
Knowledge of blood transfusion treatment	118 (77.6)	92 (75.4)	0.666

No significant association was found between gender and knowledge levels across all assessed parameters ($p > 0.05$), indicating comparable awareness between male and female parents.

Table 6: Association Between Age Group and Knowledge Levels

Knowledge Indicator	20-25 yr (n=27) n (%)	25-30 yr (n=85) n (%)	30-35 yr (n=79) n (%)	>40 yr (n=83) n (%)	p-value
Knowledge that thalassemia is genetic	18 (66.7)	61 (71.8)	56 (70.9)	58 (69.9)	0.964
Knowledge of the inheritance pattern	17 (63.0)	59 (69.4)	55 (69.6)	58 (69.9)	0.913
Awareness of complications	18 (66.7)	61 (71.8)	55 (69.6)	58 (69.9)	0.965

Age showed no significant association with knowledge levels ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that awareness was consistent across all age groups of parents.

Table 7: Association Between Premarital Testing Practice and Knowledge Levels

Knowledge Indicator	Had Premarital Testing (n=102) n (%)	No Premarital Testing (n=172) n (%)	p-value
Knowledge of genetic inheritance	78 (76.5)	111 (64.5)	0.040*
Awareness of consanguineous marriage risk	68 (66.7)	90 (52.3)	0.020*
Knowledge that thalassemia is preventable	71 (69.6)	100 (58.1)	0.058
Support for mandatory premarital testing	69 (67.6)	90 (52.3)	0.013*

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Significant associations were observed between premarital testing practice and knowledge levels. Parents who had undergone premarital testing demonstrated significantly better knowledge of genetic inheritance (76.5% vs 64.5%, $p=0.040$), awareness of consanguineous marriage risks (66.7% vs 52.3%, $p=0.020$), and support for mandatory premarital testing (67.6% vs 52.3%, $p=0.013$) compared to those who had not undergone testing.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal that parents of thalassemic children in Peshawar possess moderate to good knowledge about certain aspects of thalassemia while demonstrating significant gaps in other critical areas requiring targeted educational interventions. The observed knowledge level of 70.44% regarding the genetic nature of thalassemia is notably higher than findings from recent studies in Balochistan, where only 13.7% of parents recognized thalassemia as an inherited disease [10]. This substantial disparity underscores the crucial role of regional differences in healthcare infrastructure and awareness programs, as well as the potential impact of foundation-based support systems like Fatimid Foundation in enhancing

disease understanding among affected families. Similarly, the 92% awareness level about thalassemia in our study far exceeds the 66% reported in Malakand Division [7] and the 53% found in urban Karachi general population studies [11], emphasizing the concentrated knowledge within registered thalassemia families while highlighting critical knowledge gaps in the broader community.

The finding that 76.3% of participants recognized that proper treatment enables a normal life with thalassemia aligns with but exceeds the 58% reported by Naz et al. in a tertiary care hospital study [12], further supporting the premise that registered thalassemia families develop superior disease comprehension through structured foundation support and regular medical follow-ups. The 82.1% correct response regarding fatality of untreated thalassemia closely parallels Maheen et al.'s Karachi study reporting 97% [13], confirming that affected families universally understand the serious consequences of inadequate treatment, likely reinforced by witnessing disease complications in their children.

Regarding treatment modalities, 76.64% correctly identified blood transfusion as essential therapy,

which is consistent with the 81.1% reported in a recent Balochistan study, where blood transfusion was seen as the only treatment [10]. However, the alarming finding that 50.73% believed surgery can treat thalassemia, while slightly better than Haq et al.'s study reporting 80% misconception [14], still indicates a dangerous misunderstanding about disease management that could lead to inappropriate treatment seeking and delayed appropriate care. The finding that only 27% correctly recognized that no cure exists for thalassemia reveals a critical gap requiring immediate attention, as unrealistic expectations about a cure may affect treatment adherence and acceptance of long-term management strategies.

Knowledge about complications revealed that 70.07% understood multisystem involvement, yet only 59.12% specifically identified iron overload as the primary complication source. This gap is particularly concerning given that iron toxicity represents the primary cause of morbidity and mortality in transfused patients, leading to cirrhosis, cardiomyopathy, and endocrine disorders that are preventable through effective iron chelation therapy [4]. The long-term consequences of iron overload, including damage to mitochondria, lysosomes, and DNA through oxidative stress, require comprehensive patient education to ensure adherence to chelation therapy [15].

Genetic inheritance understanding showed encouraging results with 68.98% correctly identifying the autosomal recessive pattern requiring both carrier parents, significantly exceeding Ghafoor et al.'s general population study, where only 40.5% understood this concept [16]. This finding reinforces that targeted education to affect families yields results. However, the 50% correct response regarding single carrier parent risk and 34.67% unaware that thalassemia minor individuals lead healthy lives demonstrates persistent gaps in understanding carrier implications that directly impact reproductive decision-making. According to NHS guidelines, if both parents are carriers, there is a 1 in 4 chance with each pregnancy of having a child with thalassemia major, and

carriers themselves lead completely healthy lives [17].

The consanguineous marriage awareness of 57.66% recognizing increased risk remains concerning low, given that cousin marriages account for a substantial proportion of thalassemia cases in Pakistan. A recent study in Sargodha found that cousin marriages accounted for 79% of thalassemia patients, with 86% of affected families reporting consanguineous unions [18]. Similarly, research in the Makran division revealed that religious beliefs and family traditions significantly influence reproductive decisions among parents of thalassemic children [19]. The Balochistan Thalassemia Prevention Act now mandates premarital thalassemia testing, yet implementation remains challenging due to cultural norms and limited awareness [20].

The significant associations between premarital testing practice and enhanced knowledge of inheritance ($p=0.040$), consanguinity risks ($p=0.020$), and support for mandatory testing ($p=0.013$) suggest that undergoing testing itself serves as an educational intervention. This finding strongly supports arguments for making premarital testing universally accessible and potentially mandatory, as advocated by recent policy papers highlighting that compulsory premarital screening can significantly mitigate the burden of thalassemia major on society and healthcare systems [21].

Comparisons with international literature reveal interesting patterns. Basu's Kolkata study found 92% avoiding consanguineous marriages [22], substantially higher than our 57.66% risk awareness, reflecting cultural differences in marriage practices and perhaps more effective public health messaging in India. Similarly, Italian and Cypriot populations with longstanding national prevention programs demonstrate near-universal awareness exceeding 90% [23], highlighting what structured governmental intervention can achieve. Pakistan's position, with moderate knowledge among affected families but limited general population awareness, represents an intermediate stage where targeted interventions could yield substantial improvements.

The lack of significant association between demographic factors (gender, age) and knowledge levels ($p > 0.05$) suggests that within affected families, disease exposure overrides typical educational and demographic disparities, creating relatively uniform knowledge distribution. This finding aligns with research among future healthcare providers in Rahim Yar Khan, where 73.5% demonstrated good knowledge regardless of demographic background [24]. However, the significant associations with premarital testing practice emphasize that personal experience with screening creates lasting knowledge enhancement and attitude change.

These findings collectively paint a picture of reasonable disease-specific knowledge among affected families coexisting with critical gaps in prevention understanding and persistent misconceptions about treatment. The discrepancy between knowing thalassemia is preventable (62.41%) and actually undergoing premarital testing (37.23%) represents the central challenge facing Pakistan's thalassemia control efforts. With hereditary diseases affecting nearly 60% of the population due to consanguineous unions [6], this prevention-to-action gap must be addressed through multifaceted interventions combining public education, healthcare provider training, accessible testing services, and appropriate policy frameworks that respect cultural sensitivities while prioritizing disease prevention [25].

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that parents of thalassemic children in Peshawar possess moderate knowledge about disease characteristics and management, with over 70% understanding the genetic basis and 92% aware of the condition. However, significant knowledge gaps persist regarding disease complications, genetic inheritance patterns, and preventive strategies. Only half of the participants correctly understand carrier implications, one-third are unaware that thalassemia minor individuals lead healthy lives, and critically, fewer than 40% have undergone premarital testing despite most believing the disease is preventable. The significant association between premarital testing experience and

enhanced knowledge underscores the educational value of screening programs. These findings indicate an urgent need for comprehensive public awareness campaigns, mandatory premarital screening programs, enhanced genetic counseling services, and healthcare provider education to address knowledge gaps and reduce thalassemia prevalence in Pakistan. The government, healthcare institutions, and civil society must collaborate to implement evidence-based prevention strategies that have proven effective in other high-prevalence countries.

Limitations

This study's limitations include single-center data collection, limiting generalizability, a cross-sectional design preventing assessment of knowledge retention over time, non-probability sampling potentially introducing selection bias, and descriptive analysis level limiting causal inferences. Future research should employ multi-center designs with probability sampling, including general population comparison groups, and utilize multivariate analysis to identify independent predictors of knowledge.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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